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Corresponding Author:
Dr. Jawad Ahmed Hameed,
Medicare Hospital Attock
jawadahmedhameed11@gmail.com

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**PREVALENCE OF ACUTE TONSILLITIS
AMONG THE PATIENTS PRESENTING IN
OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT**

AUTHORS:
1. DR. WAMIQ IJAZ, FARYAL DENTAL COLLEGE
2. DR. MINAHIL RAZZAQ, PUNJAB DENTAL HOSPITAL, LAHORE
3. DR. JAWAD AHMED HAMEED, MEDICARE HOSPITAL ATTOCK

ABSTRACT:
Tonsillitis is inflammation of the tonsils in the upper part of the throat. Tonsillitis is a type of pharyngitis that typically comes on fast (rapid onset). Symptoms may include sore throat, fever, enlargement of the tonsils, trouble swallowing, and large lymph nodes around the neck. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history and duration of acute tonsillitis were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 70 patients presenting in outdoor were included in this study i.e., 35 males (50%) and 35 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 32.45±5.12 years. Out of 70 patients, seven patients presented with the acute tonsillitis and that they were taking treatment for that.

Keyword: Acute Tonsillitis

INTRODUCTION:

Tonsillitis is inflammation of the tonsils in the upper part of the throat. Tonsillitis is a type of pharyngitis that typically comes on fast (rapid onset). Symptoms may include sore throat, fever, enlargement of the tonsils, trouble swallowing, and large lymph nodes around the neck. Complications include peritonsillar abscess. Tonsillitis is most commonly caused by a viral infection and about 5% to 40% of cases are caused by a bacterial infection. When caused by the bacterium group A streptococcus, it is referred to as strep throat. Rarely bacteria such as *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, or *Haemophilus influenzae* may be the cause. Typically the infection is spread between people through the air. A scoring system, such as the Centor score, may help separate possible causes. Confirmation may be by a throat swab or rapid strep test.

Treatment efforts involve improving symptoms and decreasing complications. Paracetamol (acetaminophen) and ibuprofen may be used to help with pain. If strep throat is present the antibiotic penicillin by mouth is generally recommended. In those who are allergic to penicillin, cephalosporins or macrolides may be used. In children with frequent episodes of tonsillitis, tonsillectomy modestly decreases the risk of future episodes. About 7.5% of people have a sore throat in any three-month period and 2% of people visit a doctor for tonsillitis each year. It is most common in school-aged children and typically occurs in the colder months of fall and winter. The majority of people recover with or without medication. In 40% of people, symptoms resolve within three days, and in 80% symptoms resolve within one week, regardless of whether streptococcus is present. Antibiotics decrease symptom duration by approximately 16 hours. Those with tonsillitis usually experience sore throat, painful swallowing, malaise, and fever. Their tonsils – and often the back of the throat – appear red and swollen, and sometimes give off a white discharge. Some also have tender swelling of the cervical lymph nodes.

Many viral infections that cause tonsillitis will also cause cough, runny nose, hoarse voice, or blistering in the mouth or throat. Infectious mononucleosis

can cause the tonsils to swell with red spots or white discharge that may extend to the tongue. This can be accompanied by fever, sore throat, cervical lymph node swelling, and enlargement of the liver and spleen. Bacterial infections that cause tonsillitis can also cause a distinct "scarletiform" rash, vomiting, and tonsillar spots or discharge. Tonsilloliths occur in up to 10% of the population frequently due to episodes of tonsillitis (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history and duration of acute tonsillitis were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 70 patients presenting in outdoor were included in this study i.e., 35 males (50%) and 35 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 32.45 ± 5.12 years. Out of 70 patients, seven patients presented with the acute tonsillitis and that they were taking treatment for that.

DISCUSSION:

Viral infections cause 40 to 60% of cases of tonsillitis. Many viruses can cause inflammation of the tonsils (and the rest of throat) including adenovirus, rhinovirus, coronavirus, influenza virus, parainfluenza virus, coxsackievirus, measles virus, Epstein-Barr virus, cytomegalovirus, respiratory syncytial virus, and herpes simplex virus. Tonsillitis can also be part of the initial reaction to HIV infection. An estimated 1 to 10% of the cases are caused by Epstein-Barr virus. Tonsillitis can also stem from infection with bacteria, predominantly Group A β -hemolytic streptococci (GABHS), which causes strep throat. Bacterial infection of the tonsils usually follows the initial viral

infection. When tonsillitis recurs after antibiotic treatment for streptococcus bacteria, it is usually due to the same bacteria as the first time, which suggests that the antibiotic treatment was not fully effective.

Less common bacterial causes include: *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, *Chlamydia pneumoniae*, *Bordetella pertussis*, *Fusobacterium sp.*, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, *Treponema pallidum*, and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*. Anaerobic bacteria have been implicated in tonsillitis, and a possible role in the acute inflammatory process is supported by several clinical and scientific observations. Sometimes tonsillitis is caused by an infection of spirochaeta and treponema, which is called Vincent's angina or Plaut-Vincent angina. Within the tonsils, white blood cells of the immune system destroy the viruses or bacteria by producing inflammatory cytokines like phospholipase A2, which also lead to fever. The infection may also be present in the throat and surrounding areas, causing inflammation of the pharynx. There is no firm distinction between a sore throat that is specifically tonsillitis and a sore throat caused by inflammation in both the tonsils and also nearby tissues. An acute sore throat may be diagnosed as tonsillitis, pharyngitis, or tonsillopharyngitis (also called pharyngotonsillitis), depending upon the clinical findings (4-6).

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